

Defashionization for Sustainability: From Conspicuous to Conscientious Consumption Breaking Business Cycles for Environmentalism

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ABSTRACT: The time for defashionization has come. With the United Nations Conference of the Parties COP26 heralding the call for attention to sustainable fashion, society is ripe to question the whims of fashion's impact on sustainability. Is the luxury moment of our time harmony with nature and practicing degrowth in recycling to cherish sustainability? Already in the historic political economy foundations of capitalism, workers are described to produce in order to consume. Classic business cycle theory and the creative entrepreneur portray a human-innate need for change and innovation as the spring feather of capitalism. In capitalist societies, there is a race for innovation of entrepreneurs and offering new products on a constant basis in order to evade the falling rate of profit. Capitalist constantly innovate in order to offer new products in markets and reap the highest rate of return and profit from consumers, who constantly want to change and have access to changing products. Producers of goods are in a competitive race for innovation and offering new products to ever-innovation-seeking consumers. The constant pressure to innovate and offer new products on the supply side and the constant production for a salary in order to consume the newest goods and services lie at the core of capitalist societies. Climate change and the Sustainable Development Goals but also the Green New Deals in the United States and Europe as well as the New Generation EU have formulated aspirational goals of sustainability. The circular economy and conscientious consumption have become the *en vogue* trends of our times. The novel Coronavirus crisis COVID-19 has also driven demand for rest, recovery and degrowth. COVID Long Haulers in particular appear to favor harmony with the environment in agrohoods driving trends of deurbanization but also biophilia trends that resemble nature in interior design and clean unprocessed nutrition. How is our classic understanding of business cycles' reinvention drive and the innovative entrepreneurs' creative destruction justified in light of sustainability pledges? Have we reached an age of luxury in the appreciation of environmentalism that forms a larger transcending *Gestalt* that benefits future generations? This article asks if the time is ripe for a defashionization of economic business cycles of reproduction and harmonize ecology with innovation. The paper also provides vivid examples of sustainability capitalism solutions, which prove that the Green New Deal aligns economic values with sustainability. The New Deals, degrowth, minimalism, biophilia and agrohoods are newest trends that appear to crowd out whims of ever-changing trends for rest in sustainable well-being.

KEYWORDS: Agrohoods, Biophilia, Business Cycle Theory, Capitalism, Capitalist societies, Change, Circular economy, Climate Change, Competition, COP26, Conscientious consumption, Consumption, Creative destruction, Defashionization, Degrowth, Demand, Ecology, Economics, Economics of the Environment, Entrepreneur, Environmental Governance, European Green Deal, European Sustainable Finance Taxonomy, Falling rate of profit, Green New Deal, Innovation, Luxury, Markets, Minimalism, Next Generation EU, Political economy, Production, Reinvention, Rescue and recovery aid, Redistribution, Reproduction, Social Justice, Socially Responsible Investment, Supply, Sustainability, Sustainable Development Goals, Sustainable fashion

Business Cycle Theory

Economic growth is at the core of modern capitalism. Long-term growth trends feature periods of rapid economic growth (expansion or boom) followed by periods of relative stagnation or decline

(contractions, busts or recessions). There is an inherent character of economic fluctuations in the economy (Brenner 2006; Keynes 1936/2003; Marx 1867/1995; Schumpeter 1949; Soros 2003). Recurrent patterns of economic growth are followed by economic downturns (Puaschunder 2020a).

In the history of economic thought, economic cycles have become substantial determinants of economic forecasts. Business cycles are believed to be riding on longer-term economic cycles and in their totality sum up to influence economic industry upswings and downturns. While economic cycles capture fluctuations in the gross domestic product (GDP), business cycles are more determined by industry influences. Within industries, innovation drives demand and therefore determines the economic outlook of industries. Business cycles are the most visible elements of economic intrinsic dynamics, including a fast (3 to 5-year) inventory cycle, a medium term (7 to 10 year) fixed capital and possibly longer structures cycles. Business cycle studies identify two types of recurrent aggregate fluctuation tied to investments and innovation: (1) inventory cycles on the order of three to five years and (2) equipment cycles of about seven to eleven years, which both underlie long waves of forty-five to sixty years (Shaikh 2016). Inventory cycles are linked to balance between demand and supply, while capital equipment is linked to the balance between capacity and actual output (Shaikh 2016).

The logic of profit drives the economic system to repeat powerful business cycles, which go hand-in-hand with socio-economic fallouts (Puaschunder 2021b). In the build-up to every general economic crisis, the price of gold shoots up relative to the price of other commodities. Booms are greatly enhanced by a sharp drop in interest rates, which raises the net rate of return on capital. Falling interest rates lubricate the spread of capital across the globe, promote a rise in consumer debt and fuel international bubbles in finance and real estate (Shaikh 2016). With falling interest rates and credit being made easier, consumers and other spending continues to rise, buoyed on a rising tide of debt (Shaikh 2016). Economic crashes occur if people realize that this is not sustainable anyone. A recession is a significant decline in economic activity spread across the economy, lasting more than a few months, normally visible in real GDP, real income, employment, and industrial production (Shaikh 2016). Depression is characterized by high unemployment and falling prices.

Contemporary studies of business cycles and long-term waves capture the relation of export, investment and raw materials on economic ups and downs alongside the role of institutions (Armstrong, Glyn & Harrison 1991; Brenner 2002). At the core of economic growth is productivity. Productivity growth is associated with technical change and technological progress in capitalist development. At the most granular level, productivity is based on production and consumption. Production equals supply and consumption demand. Production and consumption are imperative for capitalist firms, rooted in the nature of profit-driven competition. In order to create constant demand, corporations need to produce innovative goods and services that entertain a human-imbued drive for change, which nurtures consumption as the ultimate driver of a modern market economy. Creative entrepreneurs are at the forefront of offering innovative goods and services that grab the attention of many and reap the highest margins at the point of market leadership based on new market introductions. As corporations face competition, other market followers will always follow in joining successful goods' production. Firms will therefore always face downward sloping demand curves and falling rates of profit in the long run. As the competitive race for innovations and market followership will always lead to dropping margins on the long run, producers are always driven by general market forces to reinvent new goods and services in either completely new domains or variations of the old.

Innovation as economic driver

Individuals like to be part of social groups and adhere to social norms and customs. But within the social status quo, individuals also like to carve out their own interpretation of something different

and novel. The wish to distinguish oneself from the status quo in possessing something new is as old as humankind. The drive to change is innate in all human beings. Human like to change and enjoy new goods and services once a while. Fashion trends and conspicuous consumption live on the notion to build on something customary old but break with trends in order to enjoy the new and individual interpretation of trends. Consuming new trends on a constant basis is part of social status enhancement (Veblen 1899), which has been practiced throughout the history of humankind.

Arts, fashion and lifestyle progress is driven by innovation. Based on purchasing power, innovation is a status insignium by the elite. As a symbol of excellence, consuming innovation is a sign of access to cultural and material capital (Bourdieu 1979/2010). Innovation appears to help society to progress economically.

The societal value of production for the elite was first outlined by Thorstein Veblen's (1899) trickling down of excellence argument. In allowing the elite to set itself apart from the general populace through conspicuous consumption, the general population has an incentive to aspire to reach such excellence one day, which drives general productivity and economic output. In consumption of luxury goods lies also what John Maynard Keynes (1936/2003) describes as multiplier effect – that a spending on consumption or investment positively vitalizes the overall economy as for multiplying in general productivity throughout the economy. The consumption of luxury trickles down through all societal ranks by creating output, jobs, salaries and other economic productivity. Luxury hence has a deeper societal meaning beyond the pure consumption. Not only being a symbolic status symbol of the elite but also does luxury serve society as economic driver that echoes positively in very many explicit and implicit ways.

Thomaï Serdari's (2016) framework explains the magic of luxury as ultimate driver of innovation and progress as for its deeper societal meaning. Serdari (2016) concretely analyzes collaborations between artists and luxury that have a long tradition. Serdari's framework draws on work of Jean-Jacques Rousseau (1750), Thorstein Veblen (1899), Max Weber (1905/1958), Pierre Bourdieu (1979), Christopher Berry (1994), Jeremy Jennings (2007), Jean-Noël Kapferer and Vincent Bastien (2009) – which represents about 250 years of collective knowledge on luxury. Luxury becomes portrayed as a winning idea and economic driver that apparently has been guiding human behavior and motivation throughout history. Serdari (2016) derives novel insights on luxury and brings together the various disciplines represented writing on the art of luxury, ranging from philosophy, sociology, anthropology, psychology, politics, economics and religion.

The economic merits of luxury as an outcome of excellence striving become apparent in the European royal courts' technical knowledge that was tied to political authority, morality and wisdom. Innovative and ingenious tools became part of the *Kunstammer* that displayed scientific instruments, automata and clocks. The most ambitious endeavors at that time were the creation of machines that could mimic human motion and seem to react intelligently to commands. The ambition even led to astonishing figural automata that could walk and gesture as if being living human beings. The automated chess player of Wolfgang von Kempelen or poem writing machinery represented the paramount of innovation at their times.

Artistic luxury excellence is at the core of the beginnings of economic fortune. Exhibits from the Renaissance, Baroque and early Enlightenment periods capture a transformative era in Europe, in which the pursuit of competitive marvelous sparked economic innovation. The striving for excellence and the joy in luxury drive economic advancement. Competitive striving for luxury by the elite became the ultimate driver of innovation leading to economic growth. Striving for bundling of excellence in luxury has a deeper cultural meaning and economic impact.

From the Renaissance to the Enlightenment, excellence expressed status through ingeniously crafted inventions (Making Marvels 2019). Collecting luxury practices but also striving for excellence gave rise to courtly marvels that were central to the inspiration for the early growth of the economy. As never before in history, the early modern period intertwined art with knowledge driving economic innovations. Royals flaunted their wealth and competed

for mastery over the known world. European rulers fashioned their identities via luxury display and competitive striving for excellence, which triggered significant advancements in astronomy, engineering and international politics. The earliest forerunners of modern science innovations became celebrated in highest craft mastery exhibited by the most precious natural materials one could find in the world.

International trade had just started to bring luxury items together with knowledge, science, technology and natural resources in the high courts of Europe. Royalty celebrated the combination of arts, science and wealth as a centralization of power and dominance. Education in science, craft and natural philosophy became the foundation of the monarchs' ultimate leadership and rule in the world and a driver of the flourishing modern world economies dominant all over the discovered world. The works were breaking innovation at that time. For European rulers, the exploration of nature was part of the demonstration of ultimate power and eternity. Owning objects that spoke to new developments in science and technology helped further one's reputation as wise, judicious ruler. Though paramount of utilitarian thoughts in the measurement, philosophy and entertainment at that time, these demonstrations of power were delightful to consume as superbly designed and adorned with most precious decorative arts. The importance of the artworks had a vast influence on astronomy, engineering, craftsmanship and international politics that lasts to this day.

But the marvelous innovations that engaged and delighted the senses of the past also hold most valuable lessons of the relation of luxury excellence and societal progress. One of the most powerful insights derived from fashion luxury in the history of humankind is that excellence symbolized by innovation is only tolerated if it can be consumed by many or create good for the masses or over time. In the grand theme of history, examining the indestructible nature over time that showcase characteristics of untouched luxury in bundling excellence that can be consumed by the many, the eternal character becomes apparent. While monarchy has been abolished or has had to be adjusted to modern democracy, the role of luxury as driver of innovation is still present to this day. In the awe-evoking delight to enjoy these opulent status insignia and power display, wealth is somehow miraculously connected to scientific possibility that teaches us values still existent to this day.

So after centuries of fashionable luxury celebration, society has learned that centralization of wealth appears to only be accepted and the culture, arts and luxury over time if they were inclusive for all societal groups. Luxury that is only owned by the few haves, yet which is resistant to the have-not's destruction thanks to the collective experience to consume beauty and pride. Imagine the example of European revolutions, in which royals were either executed, exiled or stripped of all rights to power. What survived though, was the clean and pure cultural heritage, which lasted due to a shared moment of joy or the beauty in common consumption opportunities – if one imagines the open palais, music, arts and intellectual advancements of equal access to opportunities for all. The importance of display of innovation and share of expertise survived those times, which allowed for the acceptance and perseverance of trends that were transported to the entire world and many generations to follow through marvels that were simply too beautiful to destroy and too insightful and valuable to be forgotten. The pursuit of the marvelous luxury at high European royal courts was closely associated with the quest for innovation that drove economies forward and excelled in the share of expertise with society. The remaining exhibits of those times but also the intellectual legacy provide the most fascinating examples of the conservation and preservation of luxury if forming a unique Gestalt that is too beautiful to separate and too important as for not being shared for the common good and enlightening many generations to follow.

The renaissance became known for a rebirth of humanistic values. Excellence striving of everyone and bundling of power in the European courts became unprecedentedly linked to self-determination and equal access to personal enhancement. The post-pandemic world celebrated luxury but bundled power in society became linked to a Gestalt greater than its components. Luxury and power display were only acceptable if serving the common good fostering social

identity in collectively-shared experiences. Ground-breaking innovations demonstrating mastery over nature of the world, such as the big inventions of the times – like measurement of distances and mechanization to replace scarce human labor – were clearly linked to a higher means and deeper purpose to serve the masses (Making Marvels 2019; Puaschunder 2020a; Rousseau 1750; Serdari 2016; Tajfel & Turner 1979).

Between 1550 and 1750, royal dynasties in Europe assembled vast collections of valuable and entertaining objects representing truly spectacular inventions. From the sixteenth through the eighteenth centuries, European royalty embodied the possession of beauty conveyed in innovative, artistic and technological rule. The remarkably creative outpouring of learning gave rise to exquisite objects of artistic and innovative moments shared with social capital alike. Luxury and the contexts in which excellence was bred but also the collective experience of shared benefits of striving were closely connected to royal leadership and eternal power. Innovation, technology and spectacle come together in wondrous works of art and science.

Innovative tools, scientific instruments, stylized automata and luxury clocks expressed wealth and mastery of the world in a predominance over nature. Concentrated public funds went into lavish luxury display as an expression of ultimate power and status. Through a fascinating range of objects including clocks, automata, furniture, jewelry and fashion, royal courts discovered that marvelous innovations that first ignited modern transformations in society. From the Renaissance to the Enlightenment, these marvels inspired extraordinary advances in science, technology and the arts with an impetus that echoed in political strategies, economic calculus but also the ethics of innovation.

Over the centuries, luxury insignia have been conserved and admired by the masses. To this day, arts, fashion and lifestyle is driven by luxury, a form of excellence only reachable by the elite. Although today's luxury may not be created in European courts on public spending, we can still – to this day – learn from these historic grand luxury creations' eternal values. The beauty and fascination of luxury survived throughout different times and contrary regimes. Up to today, these gems continue to mesmerize as unique experiences that are too beautiful to fail, too commonly-shared to be destroyed and too much of a Gestalt to be apart imbuing excellence displayed in luxury an eternal life. The luxury exhibits symbolized to this day appears as most advanced showcase of the deeper meaning of luxury in society than its pure visible joyful merits: As the amalgamation of artistic creation in light of European royal competition would break technological innovations that set the ground for modernism and engage crowds to contribute and stand in for the ennobling common wealth. Luxury and the striving for excellence hold invaluable insights but also ethical imperatives for the importance of excellence in society with a social component that can enlighten the masses and many generations to follow.

Art, science and entertainment was perfected at European royal courts that revolutionized our thinking in the artistic, scientific and societal worlds. Innovation and common endeavors found in luxury moments influence society and the economy. But in stark contrast to the luxury and excellence that belonged only to a few of the past, today this cultural heritage reminds about the strengthened call that heralds for inclusion as a prerequisite of our times for well-being of the many. European courts amassed an impressive display of luxury items marked by superior craftsmanship, ingenious functionality and sparkling materials. Like no other good, luxury – to this day – symbolizes pure excellence that is not only widely tolerated in society but also endeavored to be conserved. There is an implicit acceptance of excellence in form of luxury if coupled with artistic beauty, representing a common Gestalt that is more than its pieces and being shared with the greater society for the public good and advancement of humanity. Artistic leadership in the luxury world appears somewhat unique and its excellence too beautiful and unique to fail. Unique creativity derived from interdisciplinary ideas exchange creates a one-of-a-kind Gestalt that is more than its parts, which naturally leads towards preservation and conservation of these exquisite goods. This Gestalt gains implicit acceptance if luxurious artistic beauty can be consumed by all and the benefits become valuable for the greater masses and many generations to come. Lavish luxury becomes a driver of innovation and catalyst for

economic growth when a grand unique Gestalt lures peoples' natural inclination towards the conservation and preservation and if the sheer beauty of luxury can be consumed by all in common experiences that are sustainable over time.

Over the centuries and in different parts of the world with diverse cultures, luxury has played a vital role to showcase beauty, joy and entertainment. Beauty bundled in luxury leverages untouchable objects as too grand to fail. The too-big-to-fail theory asserts that specific conglomerates are so large and influential due to their interconnectivity in markets that a failure would be economically disastrous. For instance, governments provide support and protection to too-important-to-fail entities in recognition of the negative consequences for the broader economy. A disorderly failure of these too-big-to-fail objects is arguably believed to raise larger costs to the society as a whole than preserving them. Common means of avoiding destruction are protection plans and conservation attempts of governments but also global governance institutions – such as bailouts of too-big-to-fail entities for the sake of economic efficiency in an interconnected economy or the United Nations world cultural heritage protection. Drawing from the too-big-to-fail argument in economics, excellence may be seen as too powerful of a driver of the economy to be destroyed bestowing luxury an eternal character but at the same time creating a responsibility for fashion trends to be embracing sustainability.

In a full Gestalt, there is such a connection among the individual items that can be more important, more useful, more beautiful, or in some other way greater than all of the separate parts on their own. This is known as synergy and can be found everywhere in nature. For example, architecture is a unique interrelation between material and architectural form strengthened by design, innovation, technology and society's support.

Excellence in the luxury world is a unique driver of innovation. Luxury may uniquely be pegged to creative thinking, craftsmanship, art and production of timeless objects with cultural significance, which is unique and can progress society as a whole (Serdari 2016). Luxury features an excessive creative presence in the marriage of different disciplines. The coupling of ideas in a unique way spearheads human progress. The excessive element in luxury, the consumption without reason is a somewhat unique extravagance, in which superiority is widely accepted – even by the mass of people who do not have access to luxury. In the case of luxury, a lacking access to power or influence appears to be taken for granted without the destruction of excellence because the implicit economic by-products of luxury are beneficial for all.

The case of luxury accounts for accepted excellence if being shared with others – explicitly such as in a watch that can tell time for all or implicitly in economic growth driving elements. John Maynard Keynes' (1936/2003) multiplier theory outlines that excellence as economic growth driver exerts a positive effect on all as for trickling down. The consumption of luxury trickles down through all societal ranks as it will create output, jobs, salaries and very many other economic productivity drivers. For instance, a luxury endeavor may need a cadre of employees working together, that create jobs but also produce skills advancement. A stable salary ensures security within a community. Skills development and training on the job are drivers of the economy and general welfare.

In luxury, elitism appears to be justified as for boosting the overall standard of living for all individuals in the long run via economic growth. More concretely, bundled wealth is believed to incentivize, raise output and create jobs. Wealthy, competition and demand ultimately spur economic growth. Society ultimately benefits from trickle-down economics as their standard of living increases. Trickle-down economics thereby rests at the assumption that excellence will breed through the economic growth sprung out of innovation and excellence benefiting all.

Defashionization

The climate change crisis heralded unprecedented challenges for humankind. Global efforts to mitigate and adapt to global warming have risen steadily in the most recent decades. Climate

change awareness concurrent with the Coronavirus pandemic triggered a sustainability awareness. The pandemic drove a deurbanization trend in the United States of movement to environmentally-pleasant surroundings. During the outbreak of COVID, corporations offered to opt for home offices and many of the corporate headquarters have moved to less crowded, more suburban locations. Cities are still seen as disadvantaged to control large crowds and ventilation in skyscrapers. Current home owner booms in remote areas like Arizona, Texas or Florida speak for people's preference to escape cities during a pandemic.

Living in suburbs allowed a remote workforce to build wellness cocoons with attention for healthy living embedded in nature. New community development in harmony with nature are forming in so-called agri- or agrohoods. These neighborhoods are spreading all over the United States that are directly attuned to the surrounding and celebrate the natural and cultural heritage.

The ongoing ecowellness trends has not only changed our perception of closeness and contact with others, it has also revolutionized interior design in offices with glass and plastic protection. Outdoors city and landscape have been shaped by deurbanization as well. The environment became also prominent to be represented in booming biophilic architecture trends that resembles nature.

Attention to healthy nutrition is on the rise due to the pandemic and vegan lifestyles are also substantial sustainability catalysts. Especially for so-called COVID Long Haulers, who appear to suffer longer from a COVID infection than the usual recovery time, unprocessed 'clean' food has become a substantial part of recovery. Long Haulers often report cognitive overload and fatigue as well as food-related inflammation flare-ups. Long Haulers appear to have a craving for minimalistic stimulation at home that often also features a Biophilia design, which resembles nature and sustainable fabrics. With precise online retailing and people spending more time at home, minimalism is trending as people are getting rid of unnecessary items at home. All these trends combined have pushed for a demand for sustainability and recycling appreciation. The circular economy, featuring recycling and sustainable care is happening now.

One of the innovations for broad-scale environmental change were addressed during the most recent COP-26 in sustainable clothing lines made out of natural material. For instance, fungus clothing offers a carbon-negative organic alternative to fast fashion. With the most recent United Nations Conference of the Parties COP26 heralding the call for attention to sustainable fashion, society is ripe to question the whims of fashion's impact on sustainability (The New York Times, November 17, 2021).

The political economy critique of capitalism to push people to constantly produce in order to consume appears to gain momentum in light of climate change, COVID and sustainability pledges. Classic business cycle theory and the creative entrepreneur portray a human-innate need for change and innovation as the spring feather of capitalism. But in today's world, defashionization appears to give way to recycling and circular economy activities in order to meet sustainability goals. Economic advancements of our times feature the Green Deals of the United States and Europe, which marry the idea of sustainability as an economic driver and governmental multiplier that can also nudge society into a more resilient state.

Defashionization would thereby rather focus on recycling goods than producing a constant flow of waves of whims of fashion. This could stop the constant competitive race for innovation and relieve consumers from ever-innovation-seeking change and therefore also consumption pressures, which cause production pressures on the consumer end to afford continuous purchases. Defashionization could also avert the falling rate of profit and alleviate socio-economic fallouts in the race for highest rates of returns and profits.

Climate change action and the Sustainable Development Goals have formulated aspirational goals of degrowth, which advocates for focusing society away from constant growth endeavors and pressures to perform consumption and production. These relieved expectations would also be of benefit in the post-COVID-19 era for Long Haulers, who appear

to take longer time to recover and would benefit from rest and unwinding speed out of the economy. The circular economy stresses sustainability and recycling as alternative option besides capitalist consumption. Conspicuous consumption of our times may be more inspired by conscientious consumption, which is more focused on real needs rather than artificially created craves that come and go with the whims of fashion. The luxury in the era of climate change and COVID rest and recovery resilience may be found in defashionization, which breaks cycles of constant business reinvention and the innovative entrepreneurs' creative destruction for the sake of sustainability, whose fruits will be enjoyed by many generations to follow. Defashionizing economies of reproduction could harmonize ecology with innovation. The New Deals in the United States and Europe foster this new era of sustainable well-being (Puaschunder 2021a).

Defashionization holds the potential to break the recurrent patterns of economic growth followed by economic downturns, which are accompanied by negative socio-economic consequences and socio-psychological outfalls (Case & Deaton 2020). Alternative market models that build on the circular economy and recycling would not only lift the pressures on producers to constantly innovate and compete with each other for novel market introductions and consumer attention. Degrowth ideas would also offer benefits of averting downward sloping demand curves and falling rates of profit for entrepreneurs but stabilize entire market economies at a lower, yet more constant and potentially healthier and more environmentally-friendly level. Recycling and focusing away from constant consumption to impress, would also lift pressures from consumers to constantly produce and consume. It would also grant peace of mind in regards to an overload of information from marketing and advertisement, which bombards and potentially harms cognitive-overloaded COVID Long Haulers, who often report of cognitive capacity constraints, fatigue and exhaustion (Puaschunder & Gelter 2022).

While in the history of humankind, consumption of innovation was a symbol for the elite to showcase access to excellence, cultural and material capital; the time is ripe to peg excellence in innovation to sustainability goals. This luxury in de-spending on consumption but refocus on targeted needs could be driven by the understanding that resources are scarce and natural goods conservation could form a *Gestalt* that is larger than the individual craving and one generation's pleasure cruise. Innovations of our times may be greening of the economy and share of expertise how to balance consumption and growth inbetween generations (Puaschunder 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020).

As never before in history, there is a deeper inspiration for degrowth for the sake of sustainability and conscientious consumption innovations. A new form of economics of rest and recovery could become the breaking innovation at that time. The exploration of the conservation of nature could become the demonstration of ultimate power for eternity. New developments in science and technology could help further one's reputation as wise consumer who cares for the greater good over time. The most marvelous innovations of our times may hold most valuable lessons of the relation of luxury excellence and societal progress. Luxury of our days may be bundling excellence in refrained consumption for an eternal character to enjoy nature sustainably. Wealth could become somehow miraculously connected to scientific possibility to connect economics of rest and recovery with the beauty of sustained natural resources and balance of the economy with ecology.

Sustainability could become a unique *Gestalt* that is too beautiful to separate and too important as for being shared for the common good. What appears to be missing in standard Keynes' (1936/2003) multiplier effect calculus is the intertemporal consideration – that a spending on consumption or investment positively vitalizes the overall economy as for multiplying in general productivity throughout the economy but a spending on a sustainable solution may multiply and transpose value even beyond one generation. The de-consumption of luxury in recycling may trickle down to future generations. Luxury in conscientious consumption hence has a deeper societal intertemporal meaning beyond the pure consumption. Not only being a symbolic status symbol of the elite but also does luxury serve society as

economic driver that echoes positively explicit and implicit in the future to come. Wise choices or de-choices may become the innovation of our times and the legacy that our generation may leave for posterity. Living in this transformative era we may spark a new Renaissance that features economic innovation in balance with ecologic respect. The striving for excellence in sustainable lifestyles and the joy in luxury of degrowth may drive socio-economic advancement and build future capital. Striving for bundling of excellence in sustainability luxury thereby bestows a deeper cultural meaning and economic impact with lasting resilience and a collective experience of nature for eternity.

Our new renaissance could become known for a rebirth of humanistic values found in ecological respect. Luxury of our time could be serving the common good of many generations in a conscientious mastery of natural resources. Wise conservation defashionization could be clearly linked to serving the masses over time as an eternal power display in choosing sustainability over economic growth. So while the innovative tools of luxury in ancient times were a display of mastery of the world, extraordinary advances of our times in science, technology and the arts could have an impetus that echoes long after in the preservation of natural environments to be enjoyed for eternity. Over the centuries, luxury insignia could become a stable nature that was conserved and can be admired by the masses. Public spending could be pegged to causes that ensure the grand luxury of natural preservation as eternal values. Ecologic stability could become the ultimate Gestalt that enables eternal living conditions in a favorable climate. Luxury and consumption could thereby gain a deeper meaning with joyful merits over time that engages crowds and ennobles long-term common wealth. Defashionization could thereby symbolize pure excellence that cherishes nature's treasures endeavored to be conserved. New Deal projects could benefit from an implicit acceptance of excellence in form of luxury if coupled with representing a common *Gestalt* that is more than its pieces and being shared with the greater society for the public good and advancement of humanity for posterity. Nature could be interpreted as too beautiful and unique to fail that is more than its parts, which naturally leads towards preservation and conservation of these exquisite goods. This *Gestalt* gains implicit acceptance if luxurious artistic beauty can be consumed by all and the benefits become valuable for the greater masses. Drawing from the too-big-to-fail argument in economics, excellence in natural goods may be seen as too powerful of a driver of the economy to be destroyed bestowing luxury in balanced growth an eternal character. In a full *Gestalt*, this could connect individual in an intergenerational contract that is more important, more useful, more beautiful, or in some other way greater than all of the separate parts of singular generations on their own consuming without consciousness or care. All these ideas brought forward at this moment in time spearhead human progress in inclusive leadership in harmony with nature to transmit the world greater than found before.

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